

PROGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF CLINICAL, PATHOGENETIC, AND GENETIC FACTORS IN HEPATORENAL SYNDROME IN THE ARAL SEA REGION

Jabbarov A.A.

Professor at Head of department of faculty and hospital therapy Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan

doctor.azim.jabborov@gmail.com

Samadova A.B.

Assistant at Urgench Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy, department of internal disease at regional hospital of Khorezm region, Urgench, Uzbekistan

samadovaanagul756@gmail.com

Yusupova Sh.B

Assistant at Urgench Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy, department of internal disease at regional hospital of Khorezm region, Urgench, Uzbekistan

yusupovashakhlo5999@gmail.com

Abstract: Hepatorenal syndrome is a severe complication of liver cirrhosis and is a pathophysiological change of the kidneys that simultaneously leads to acute or chronic dysfunction.

Hepatorenal syndrome, in turn, includes a number of pathogenetic mechanisms: 1) detoxification dysfunction of the liver; inactivation of hormones and inactivation of biologically active substances; 2) oxidative stress, pathological damage to the endothelium, immune response, inflammation, apoptosis; 3) neuroendocrine activation (RAAT, sympathetic nervous system - vasopressin); 4) violation of water-electrolyte balance, accumulation of uremic toxins

Keywords: Portal hypertension (PH), Hepatorenal syndrome, liver cirrhosis, Child-Pyru classification, prognosis, Predisposition, RAAS.

OROLBO‘YI MINTAQASIDAGI AHOLI ORASIDA GEPATORENAL SINDROMNING KLINIK-PATOGENETIK VA GENETIK JIHATLARINI PROGNOSTIK AHAMIYATI

Annatsiya. Gepatorenal sindrom - Jigar sirrozining og‘ir asorati hisoblanib, buyraklarning patofiziologik o‘zgarishi bo‘lib, bir vaqtda o‘tkir yoki surunkali disfunktsiyasiga olib keladi.

Shuningdek Gepatorenal sindrom o‘z navbatida bir qator patogenetik mexanizmlarni o‘z ichiga oladi: 1) jigarning dezintoksikatsion disfunktsiyasi; gormonlar inaktivatsiyasi va biologic aktiv moddalar inaktivatsiyalash

funksiyasining buzilishi 2) oksidlovchi stress, endoteliyning patologik shikastlanishi, immun javob, yallig'lanish, apoptoz; 3) neyroendokrin faollashuvi (RAAT, simpatik nerv tizimi- vazopressin); 4) suv- elektrolit balansining buzilishi, uremik toksinlar to'planishi

Kalit so'zlar: Partal gipertenziya (PG), dislipoproteinemiya, Gepatorenal sindrom, Jigar sirrozi, Chayld-Pyu klassifikatsiyasi, prognozlash, RAAT

Kirish. Buyrak yoki jigar disfunktsiyasining rivojlanishi bilan RAAT va simpatik nerv tizimi faollashadi, endotelial disfunktsiya va surunkali tizimli yallig'lanish rivojlanadi. Ushbu patofiziologik mexanizmlar bir vaqtning o'zida jigar va buyrakning fibrozi hamda ularning disfunktsiyasiga sabab bo'ladi. (Bova A.A, Zhang J. Bottiglieri T., 2017)

Gepatorenal sindromning 2 tipi farqlanadi:

1. Gepatorenal sindromning 1 tipida qon zardobidagi kreatinin miqdorining 2 haftadan kam vaqt davomida yakuniy qiymati 221 mmol/l dan ikki baravar oshishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Bu odatda og'ir alkogolli gepatit epizodi yoki jigar kasalligining so'nggi bosqichida bo'lgan bemorda kuzatiladi. Davolashsiz 1- tip gepatorenal sindromning o'rtacha omon qolish muddati taxminan 2 hafta.

2. 2-toifa gepatorenal sindrom diuretiklarga chidamli astsitli bemorlarda uchraydi. Bu zardobdagi kreatininning sekinroq va kam progressiv ko'tarilishi bilan 133 mmol / l dan oshadigan qiymat bilan tavsiflanadi. U 1-toifa gepatorenal sindromga qaraganda yaxshiroq prognozga ega, o'rtacha omon qolish muddati 4-6 oy

Gepatorenal sindromni dastlabki bosqichlarida tashxislash o'z vaqtida davolash, asoratlarini oldini olish va o'lim xavfini kamaytirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Gepatorenal sindrom klinik belgilari kech bosqichlarida yuzaga kelganligi sababli jigar va buyraklarning xujayraviy shikastlanish biomarkerlarini o'rganish hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega xisoblanadi. Biomarkerlar juda sezgir va o'ziga xos bo'lishi zararlanish vaqtini, og'irligini va kasallikning kechishini bashorat qilishga imkon beradi. (Melnik A. A., Vizir V. A., Berezin A. E. va boshq., 2017). Biomarkerlar yordamida tashxislash Gepatorenal sindromning patofiziologik xavfi va bosqichini hamda, davolash natijasi va samaradorligini aniqlashga yordam beradi.

Muammoning dolzarbligi. Oxirgi yigirma yillik davomida aholi orasida jigar kasalliklaridan o'lim ko'rsatkichi sezilarli darajada kamayishiga qaramasdan, surunkali gepatit natijasida surunkali buyrak kasalligi (SBK) bilan kasallanish va o'lim ko'rsatkichi sezilarli darajada oshib bormoqda. Ushbu guruh bemorlarda xavf omillari va asoratlar mavjudligi jigar sirrozi va surunkali buyrak yetishmovchiligiga olib keladi. Buyrak disfunktsiyasi darajasi, ko'ptokcha filtratsiya tezligi kamayishi, mikroalbuminuriya darajasi, umumiy o'lim xavfi jigar kasalliklari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik borligi hozirgi kunga qadar o'rganilmoqda. (). Surunkali buyrak

kasalliklari va jigar kasalliklari asoratlari o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikni Gepatorenal sinrom atamasi bilan atash taklif qilingan. Jigar funksiyasi buzilgan bemorlarda surunkali buyrak kasalligining uchrash darajasi sog‘lom insonlarga qaraganda 64% yuqori hisoblanadi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi: Gepatorenal sindromning klinik-patogenetik va genetik jihatlarini prognostik ahamiyatini baholashdir.

Tadqiqot vazifalari:

1. SBK ning II-III bosqichlarida buyrak ko‘ptokchalarining funksional holatini aniqlash.
2. Jigar disfunktsiyasini SBK ning II-III bosqichlarida baholash.
3. PNPLA3 va HFE genlarning Gepatorenal sindromning kelib chiqishida fenotipik va genotipik omillarning klinik ahamiyatini baholash.
4. Gepatorenal sinromning rivojlanishiga turtki bo‘ladigan xavfli guruhlarini shakllantirish va informatsion genetik panelini ishlab chiqish.

Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari:

barcha o‘zbek millatiga mansub bemorlarda klinik-patogenetik va genetik (PNPLA3 va HFE), gemodinamik va zarur instrumental usullarni o‘z ichiga olgan tekshiruv usullar kiritildi. Gepatorenal sindrom bilan kasallangan bemorlarning klinik, laborator va instrumental natijalari shuni ko‘rsatadiki, o‘tkazilgan so‘rovnoma asosan bemorlarda plazmadagi umumiy billirubin miqdori o‘zgargan, albumin miqdori deyarli barcha bemorlarda o‘zgaradi, protrombin indeksi kamayadi, protrombin vaqti uzayadi, , zararli odatlar (spirtli ichimliklar ichish, chekish), nasliy moyillik ham bor. Bemorlarda gepatorenal sindromning asosiy tarkibiy qismlarining dinamikasi va tuzatish samaradorligini o‘rganildi bunda gepatorenal sindromning asosiy tarkibiy qismlarining o‘rtacha darajalari, shuningdek, jigarda bo‘ladigan o‘zgarishlar bilan bog‘liq. Shu bilan birga, billirubin, albumin protrombin miqdorining o‘zgarishi kasallikni kechishiga qarab turlicha o‘zgaradi. bila Aholining yoshi ulg‘aygan sari bu kasallik avj olishi ko‘payadi. Yosh o‘sishi bilan gepatorenal sindromning asosiy tarkibiy qismlarining o‘rtacha darajasi oshadi, shuningdek, plazmadagi umumiy billirubin oshadi, plazmadagi albumin miqdori kamayadi va kasallanish ko‘payadi.

Baholanadigan belgilar	Child-Pyu bo'yichalar guruhlar		
	A (1ball)	B (2 ball)	C (3 ball)
Plazmadagi umumiy bilirubin, mmol / l (mg / dL)	<34 mmol / L (<2 mg / Aaysh)	34-50 mmol / l (2-3 mg / Aaysh)	> 50mol / L (> 3 mg / Aaysh)
Qon plazmasi albumin , g	> 3.5 g	2.8-3.5 g	<2.8 g
Astit (qorin bo'shlig'ida suyuqlik to'planishi)	Yo'q	Davolash osonroq	Og'ir, nazorat qilish murakkab
Jigar ensefalopatiyasi	Yo'q	I-II darajali (yengil, terapevtik nazorat ostida)	III-IV darajali (og'ir, nazorat qilish murakkab)
Protrombin indeksi (PTI),%	> 60%	40-60%	<40%
protrombin vaqti (PTW), p	1-4 b	4-6 soniya	> 6 soniya
xalqaro normallashtirilgan munosabatlar (INR)	> 1.70	1.71-2.20	> 2.20

Siroz klassi barcha parametrlar bo'yicha ballar yig'indisiga qarab belgilanadi. Jami 5-6 ball A sinfga, jami 7-9 ball B sinfga va jami 10-15 ball C sinfga to'g'ri keladi.

A sinfidagi bemorlarning umr ko'rish davomiyligi 15-20 yil, qorin bo'shlig'i jarrohliligida operatsiyadan keyingi o'lim 10% ni tashkil qiladi. B klassi - jigar transplantatsiyasini ko'rib chiqish uchun ko'rsatma; Bundan tashqari, qorin bo'shlig'i jarrohliligida operatsiyadan keyingi o'lim 30% ga etadi. C toifasidagi bemorlarda umr ko'rish davomiyligi 1-3 yilga etadi va qorin bo'shlig'i jarrohliligi bilan operatsiyadan keyingi o'lim 82% ni tashkil qiladi. Child-Pugh mezonlariga asoslanib, jigar transplantatsiyasiga bo'lgan ehtiyojni baholash taklif qilindi: C sinfga mansub bemorlarda yuqori ehtiyoj, B sinfidagi bemorlarda o'rtacha va A sinfidagi bemorlarda past.

Siroz bilan og'rikan bemorlarning omon qolish darajasi bo'yicha turli taxminlar mavjud. Masalan: bir yil ichida, ikki yil ichida.

- A sinfi uchun: 100%, 85%
- B sinf uchun: 81%, 57%
- C sinfi uchun: 45%, 35%

Figura .1. Yoshga nisbatan kasallikning rivojlanishi

Xulosa. Tadqiqot natijalari Gepatorenal sindrom bilan kasallangan bemorlarning tekshiruv standartiga genetik tekshiruvlarni kiritish orqali jigar va buyrak yetishmovchiligi va asoratlarni oldini olib bemorlar hayot davomiyligini uzaytirishimiz mumkin.

References:

1. Erly, B., Carey, W., Kapoor, B., McKinney, J., Tam, M., & Wang, W. (2015). Hepatorenal Syndrome: A review of pathophysiology and current treatment options. *Seminars in Interventional Radiology*, 32(04), 445–454. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0035-1564794>
2. Flint, A. (1863, April 1). Clinical Report on Hydro-peritoneum, based on an analysis of forty-six cases. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Clinical-Report-on-Hydro-peritoneum%2C-based-on-an-of-Flint/b610e6d05d88286a9f3463f7de354b4cfe015c16>
3. Frerichs, T. (1877). *Tratado práctico de las enfermedades del hígado, de los vasos hepáticos y de las vías biliares*. Biblioteca Virtual Miguel De Cervantes. <https://www.cervantesvirtual.com/obra/tratado-practico-de-las-enfermedades-del-higado-de-los-vasos-hepaticos-y-de-las-vias-biliares/>
4. Fritsch, S. J., Blankenheim, A., Wahl, A., Hetfeld, P., Maassen, O., Deffge, S., Kunze, J., Rossaint, R., Riedel, M., Marx, G., & Bickenbach, J. (2022). Attitudes and perception of artificial intelligence in healthcare: A cross-sectional survey among patients. *Digital Health*, 8, 205520762211167. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20552076221116772>
5. Jung, C., & Chang, J. W. (2023). Hepatorenal syndrome: Current concepts and future perspectives. *Clinical and Molecular Hepatology*, 29(4), 891–908. <https://doi.org/10.3350/cmh.2023.0024>

6.Koppel, M. H., Coburn, J. W., Mims, M. M., Goldstein, H., Boyle, J. D., & Rubini, M. E. Transplantation of Cadaveric Kidneys from Patients with Hepatorenal Syndrome. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 280(25), 1367–1371. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejm196906192802501>

8.Martinez, M. O., Sayles, H., Vivekanandan, R., Souza, S. D., & Florescu, M. C. (2011). Hepatorenal syndrome: Are we missing some prognostic factors? *Digestive Diseases and Sciences*, 57(1), 210–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10620-011-1861-1>

9.Mazhnaya, A., Geurts, B., Brigida, K., Bakieva, S., Sadirova, S., Witzigmann, A., Musabaev, E., Brandl, M., Weishaar, H., Dudareva, S., & Bcheraoui, C. E. (2024). Barriers and facilitators to viral hepatitis testing in Uzbekistan: scoping qualitative study among key stakeholders, healthcare workers, and the general population. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-18953-5>

10.TNF tumor necrosis factor [Homo sapiens (human)] - Gene - NCBI. (n.d.). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/7124>

11.Samadova AB, Sattorova NA. PREVENTIVE AND DIAGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF ECG RESULTS IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS. *Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing*. 2023 Dec 22;1(9):36-9.